

correlated with larval weight. It was concluded that silica is an important component of resistance. Dead heart incidence varied in the different cultivars; it was highest in B5580 and HR59 and lowest in W1263, TN1, and TKM-6. It was intermediate in Eshwarakora and IR20. The silica content of the plant and the incidence of dead hearts were significantly negatively correlated. The application of silica at sowing was more conducive to its uptake than its application at transplanting 7 days later.

Apparently tissue hardening due to silica in the leaf sheath caused the larvae to leave that part and to bore into the stem to feed on the pith of W1263 and TKM-6. The larvae showed a marked tendency to leave TKM-6 plants, probably because of repellence. This apparent larval reaction was found to be related to plant structure; vascular bundles were arranged closely in TKM-6. The survival and growth of larvae were highest in the susceptible varieties HR59 and B5580, intermediate in W1263, IR20, and TN1, and lowest in TKM-6 and Eshwarakora. Chemical analysis of major plant constituents indicated that a variety's degree of resistance is influenced by high content of dry matter, silica, and potassium, and low content of moisture, nitrogen, and sodium.

Biotype 2 brown planthopper in the Philippines

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In October of 1975, IR26, which has the dominant gene *Bph-1* for resistance to brown planthopper, was reported to have been attacked by brown planthoppers in Barangay Toril, west of Davao City, Mindanao, southern Philippines. Field investigations confirmed the hopper and grassy stunt virus damage to IR26 and other rices with the dominant gene *Bph-1* (IR1561-228-3, IR28, and IR30). Brown planthopper attacks had been serious in the area since 1973. IR26 was first

grown there in the 1975 dry season.

In the trial of the first International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) only Ptb 21 and IR2035-255 were not wiped out by grassy stunt virus. Ninety farm trials (each covering 1/33 of a hectare) of IR2071-625-1-252 (recessive gene *bph-2* for hopper resistance) came through perfectly in Barangay Toril. IR2071-625-1-252 (which was recently named by the Philippine Seed Board as IR36) provided some 15,400 kg of seed that are resistant to both brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2. Seed growers harvested an estimated 880,000 kg of IR36 in April 1976.

IR26 is reported to have been attacked by brown planthopper throughout the southern Mindanao region where rainfall is uniformly distributed and there are no typhoons to reduce hopper population. The presence of brown planthopper biotype 2 in southern Luzon (south of Manila) was confirmed in September 1975. The Philippine Government is alerting extension workers and rice farmers to the developing situation. The 1976 insecticide and rice variety recommendations have been changed to meet the new menace of biotype 2 of the brown planthopper.

Sources of resistance to brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*

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Almost 500 indigenous varieties and foreign introductions were screened in

Percent survival of seedlings after infestation with brown planthopper. Central Rice Breeding Station, Batalagoda, Ibbagamuwa, Sri Lanka.

Variety	Survival of seedlings ^a (%)
Ptb 33	83.7
ARC 6650	78.3
Suduru Samba	76.9
MR 1523	71.2
Sudu Heenati	65.3
TN1 (susceptible check)	8.7

^aAv. of three replicates.

the greenhouse in a search for sources of resistance to local biotypes of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. The varieties were evaluated on the basis of percentage of seedlings that survived after 10 days of infestation by the second- and third-instar nymphs.

The survival of the seedlings of different varieties varied markedly and ranged from 0 to 90 percent. The table indicates the reactions of varieties that demonstrated more than 65 percent survival and which can be considered resistant to the local hopper biotype.

Varietal resistance of rice to the white-tipped nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi*

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Twenty recommended rice varieties were tested for resistance to the rice white-tipped nematode in pot inoculation trials. Tongil, Early Tongil, Tongil-chal, and Shirogane were found highly resistant. Office of Rural Development, Suweon, Republic of Korea.

Variety	Diseased culms (%)	Rating ^a
Early Tongil	0	R
Tongil	0	R
Tongil-chal	0	R
Shirogane	0	R
Norin Mochi #1	12.1	MR
Juckna	12.3	MR
Paldal	15.7	MR
Mangyeong	17.9	MR
Minehikari	20.1	MS
Akibare	20.5	MS
Satominori	20.7	MS
Pungkwang	20.8	MS
Olchal	22.3	MS
Jaekeon	23.1	MS
Suseong	26.3	MS
Jinheung	27.7	MS
Palgeum	42.2	S
Shin #2	42.2	S
Nongbaek	43.1	S
Fukunohana	46.6	S

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible.